

AEROELASTIC TAILORING OF THE COMPOSITE WING STRUCTURE VIA SHAPE FUNCTION APPROACH

Wenmin Qian¹ and Jie Zeng¹

¹ Beijing Key Laboratory of Civil Aircraft Structures and Composite Materials, Beijing Aeronautical Science & Technology Research Institute of COMAC, Future Science and Technology Park, Changping District, Beijing102211, China

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the functionality of applying a Bilinear Lagrange shape function to create the design variables for aeroelastic tailoring of a composite wing structure. Comparing to the element-based design variable approach which may generate a non-smooth thickness distribution on skin/spar, the shape function approach assumes that the thickness distribution on a wing skin or along a spar can be superimposed by a set of shape functions. In this way, the design variables become the coefficients of the shape functions. As a result, after the optimizer solves these coefficients to achieve an optimized structure, the thickness on each element can be determined by superimposing the shape function together, and the thickness distribution is also smooth. Based on a model of transport aircraft, application of the shape function approach to the aeroelastic optimization of composite wing structure is designed and analyzed, with different shape functions setting and flutter constraints, respectively. The optimization results demonstrate that the shape function approach is an efficient approach to be used in the structure sizing problems.

1 INTRODUCTION

To obtain lower fuel consumption, the primary concerns for designing a transport aircraft is increasing the lift to drag ratio, and reducing the structural weight. To increase the lift to drag ratio, high aspect ratio wings are usually adopted. However, the requirement for both minimal structural weight and high aspect ratio wing may cause a highly flexible wing structure which is prone to aeroelastic instabilities. Therefore, the aeroelastic tailoring is an important method to achieve weight saving and aeroelastic stability simultaneously. Aeroelastic tailoring can be defined as "*the embodiment of directional stiffness into an aircraft structural design to control aeroelastic deformation, static or dynamic, in such a fashion as to affect the aerodynamic and structural performance of that aircraft in a beneficial way*,"[1].

Aeroelastic tailoring has attracted a lot of attentions over the past decades. Weisshaar presented the effect of fibrous composite materials on the static aeroelastic characteristics of swept and unswept wings [2], and the potential for aeroelastic tailoring of forward swept wing was illustrated. Multi-objective optimization was applied to the tailoring problems to find the optimal combination of design variables by Layton [3], and the tailoring process was able to find aeroelastic and aeroservoelastic design that reduced the gust response by up to 10%. The wing box skins of a representative fighter configuration with multiple wing control surfaces were sized to minimum weight by Zink [4], the design process incorporated response surfaces, fast probability integration and modal-basis multidisciplinary design optimization to characterize the design space. Jutte explored the use of tow steered composite laminates, functionally graded metals, thickness distributions, and curvilinear rib/spar/stringer topologies for aeroelastic tailoring [5]. Although a strong trade-off between flutter speed and weight exists, both a 100% flutter improvement and a 3.5% weight reduction were obtained by one case. Stanford solved several minimum-mass optimizations to evaluate the effectiveness of a variety of novel tailoring schemes for subsonic transport wings [6]. In addition to a transonic flutter margin constraint, aeroelastic stress and panel buckling constraints were imposed. In order to minimize the weight of a truss-braced natural-laminar-flow composite wing, Wang applied Automated Structural Optimization System (ASTROS) for aeroelastic tailoring subject to multiple constraints [7]. The results showed that the truss-braced natural-laminar-flow composite wing with high aspect ratio

could reduce the fuel consumption significantly compared to the conventional commercial aircraft configuration. However, in this study, the design variables were the elements of spars/ribs/skins of the wing. The most commonly used element based thickness type variables in aeroelastic tailoring usually result in a non-smooth skin thickness distributions, and further increase manufacturing cost and could create local stress concentration problem. Therefore, a smooth procedure must be developed to fit the thickness distribution.

Unlike element based design variables, this paper will introduce a Bilinear Lagrange shape function to generate the thickness type design variables to overcome the skin non-smoothness problem. The shape function approach assumes that the thickness distribution on a wing skin or along a spar/stringer can be superimposed by a set of shape functions. In this way, the design variables become the coefficients of the shape functions. As a result, after the optimizer solves these coefficients to achieve an optimized result, the thickness on each element can be determined by superimposing the shape function together, and the thickness distribution is also smooth. Furthermore, one additional advantage of using shape function approach is that the number of design variables is much less than that of the element-based design variable approach.

2 BILINEAR LAGRANGE SHAPE FUNCTION

Assuming a group of adjacent plate elements such as CQUAD4/CTRIA3/CSHEAR are used to define a macro-element or triangular macro-element in a FEM model of a wing structure, after an isoparametric mapping of a macro-element from the plane of the macro-element to a square shape on a reference plane in the coordinates, the thickness distribution on this macro-element can be defined as

$$t = \sum_{i=1}^4 N_i(\xi, \eta) t_i \quad (1)$$

Where t_i is the thickness at the four corner points of the macro-element, and $N_i(\xi, \eta)$ are the four bilinear Lagrange shape functions. The four bilinear Lagrange shape functions can be given as

$$\begin{cases} N_1 = (\xi - 1)(\eta - 1) \\ N_2 = -\xi(\eta - 1) \\ N_3 = \xi\eta \\ N_4 = -(\xi - 1)\eta \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The illustration of these four bilinear Lagrange shape functions is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Four bilinear Lagrange shape functions

For example, for the i th grid point that is the common corner point shared by its adjacent macro-elements, by assigning the thickness at this grid point to unit, a design variable can be defined with the associated bilinear Lagrange shape function, and the design variable and its shape function can be shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Design variable at the i th grid point and its shape function

3 PROBLEM STATEMENT

The purpose of this research is to investigate the application of the bilinear Lagrange function as design variables for a composite wing structure design via aeroelastic tailoring. Fig.3 (a) gives the FEM of a whole transport aircraft, which contains the fuselage, wings, ailerons, horizontal tails, elevator, vertical tails, pylons and engines. In this model, the pylon structure was simulated the stiffness matrices and mass matrices with DMIG. Furthermore, the fuel mass, payload mass are simulated using CONM2s. In this study, only the wing structures of composite material, such as the upper/lower wing skin, front/rear spar, and stringer are optimized to saving the weight of the wing. The baseline of optimized wing structure is given in Fig. 3 (b).

a) The FEM of a transport aircraft

b) The baseline of the optimized wing

Figure 3: The FEM of a transport aircraft and optimized wing.

The aerodynamic shape of the aircraft is created based on the geometric profile of the transport aircraft, and it is presented in Fig. 4. The aerodynamic element of aircraft is established based on ZEUS/ZAERO. The fuselage is simulated by body elements, and the wing is divided with plate elements. Meanwhile, in order to consider the influence of the shock wave, the airfoil shape of the wing is taken into account through the PAFOIL7 card in ZAERO, just as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: The aerodynamic shape of the transport aircraft

The optimization task for the composite wing structure is operated in ASTROS [8-9], which can be defined in a mathematical form as:

Find the set of design variable, v , that can minimize an objective function:

$$F(v) \quad (3)$$

subject to constraints:

$$g_j(v) \leq 0, j=1, \dots, ncon \quad (4)$$

$$h_k(v) = 0, k=1, \dots, ne \quad (5)$$

$$v_i^{\text{lower}} \leq v_i \leq v_i^{\text{upper}}, i=1, \dots, ndv \quad (6)$$

where g specifies the $ncon$ inequality constraints, and h refers to the ne equality constraints, and Eq. (6) specifies lower and upper bounds (side constraints) on each of the design variables. $ncon$, ne , and ndv are the number of constraints and design variables respectively.

In this research, the objective function $F(v)$ is chosen as the weight of the composite wing structure, subject to the required flutter speeds, without exceeding allowable strain constraints. In addition, the design variables are the thickness of each composite layer on those elements of the composite skins and spars of the wing.

4 OPTIMIZATION FRAMEWORK

4.1 Critical design loads

The critical loads are the first key point in the optimization design, because the critical loads determine the value of the stress and the displacement. As a rule of thumb, the static deformation of the wing will change the flutter boundary of the aircraft. Therefore, the load must be representative. In this study, the loads contain two parts. The first part is the 21 critical loads which are calculated and selected from the entire aircraft flight envelope. The 21 loads includes gust loads, landing gear impact loads, and aerodynamic loads from 2.5g pull-up, -1.0g push-over and $\pm 25^\circ$ aileron deflection. The second part is obtained from ZONAIR. At the beginning, the aerodynamic pressure from CFD result or wind tunnel test is interpolated to the aerodynamic model shown in Fig. 4. Then, a static trim is computed by ZONAIR, and the aerodynamic loads are updated based on the trim results. Among the updated load, 7 critical loads are selected under the condition of 2.5g pull-up and -1.0g push-over. Finally, in ASTROS the 28 external loads are applied to the structural model through the use of input entries which define forces, moments and pressure loadings. The forces are applied at specified grid points and in a direction either defined explicitly at one input, or referred by two grid points along which the direction of the force can be defined. The moments are applied in a similar way.

4.2 Constraints

In this design, four kinds of constraints are considered in the aeroelastic tailoring. They are the strength constraint, buckling constraint, constraint of laminate stitch technology and flutter constraint respectively. For upper/lower wing skin and front/rear spar web, the strain constraint is between 0.0035 and 0.006. Meanwhile, the strain constraint of stringer and spar flange is between 0.0033 and 0.006. The buckling of the element can be solved using the eigenvalue problem. Therefore, the buckling constraint is that the minimal buckling eigenvalue is larger than 1.11. Taking into consideration of manufacture difficulty of composite material, there are some constraints for the laminate ply-up ratio and thickness. For typical ply angle, such as $[0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ]$, the ply-up ratio is limited to around [40%, 25%, 25%, 10%]. Meanwhile, the total thickness of the element must be between 4 and 24 mm, which mean that the thickness of each element is in the range of 21 and 124 layers.

The ZONA Transonic (ZTRAN) method [10] in ZAERO is employed to generate the Aerodynamic Influence Coefficient (AIC) matrices in the Mach range of [0.82~0.85]. ZTRAN tool computes the unsteady transonic aerodynamics using an overset field-panel method. It solves the time-linearized transonic small perturbation equation in which the variant coefficient terms are obtained by interpolating the high-fidelity CFD solutions using ZEUS to the volume cells. Then, the flutter boundary can be predicted using g method. These AIC matrices are imported into ASTROS to evaluate the flutter constraints at transonic Mach numbers. It is well known that for such a wing mounted engine transport aircraft studied in this paper, the fuel is stored inside the wing tanks and centre tanks. The fuel weight in the wing tanks has important effects on the flutter boundary of the aircraft, and the maximum fuel weight causes the severe flutter issue. Therefore, the flutter analysis with the consideration of the maximum fuel weight will be performed and be applied as a critical flutter constraint for aeroelastic tailoring.

The flutter boundary of the aircraft should not across the 15% margin of the aeroelastic envelope. Therefore, in this study of aeroelastic tailoring, two kinds of flutter envelope margin are considered respectively. Table 1 summarizes the flutter speed of normal aeroelastic envelope, 20% margin and 25% margin respectively while the Mach number is from 0.6 to 0.87. In Table 1, the speed is the true speed, and the value of margin is computed in equivalent speed.

Mach number	Normal aeroelastic envelope [m/s]	20% envelope margin [m/s]	25% envelope margin [m/s]
0.6	208.22	215.39	217.07
0.7	235.35	244.02	245.94
0.75	248.56	257.47	259.54
0.785	257.69	266.92	268.98
0.8	261.57	270.93	273.02
0.81	264.15	273.59	275.72
0.82	266.72	276.25	278.39
0.85	274.39	284.15	286.50
0.87	279.78	289.67	291.92

Table 1: The designed flutter margins of the aircraft in true speed

4.3 Design variables

In this aeroelastic tailoring, the same properties are used for the symmetric elements between left and right wing. Therefore, only the design variables of left wing, as shown in Fig.5, should be taken into account, the design variables will link both the elements of left wing and right wing simultaneously. As shown in Fig.5, the design variables of skin and spar web are the thickness of the element respectively. In addition to restrict the ply angles to 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° , it also requires balanced symmetric laminates, i.e., a $+45^\circ$ ply must be accompanied by a -45° ply. For 8-ply laminates of an each shell element of skin with the form $[45^\circ, -45^\circ, 0^\circ, 90^\circ, 90^\circ, 0^\circ, -45^\circ, 45^\circ]$, will need 3 design

variables. Because the stringers and spar caps are 1D truss element, each element only has one design variable, and which is cross-section area.

Figure 5: Design variables of the left wing

In order to apply bilinear Lagrange shape function to setup the design variables, the super element which is composed of many unit elements are selected, and these nodes of the super element are used as the control points, also called the design variables. The cell thickness is therefore connected to the node by the bilinear Lagrange shape function. Two kinds of distribution of control point, i.e., tight and loose distribution, are tested to evaluate the influence of control points on the results of aeroelastic tailoring respectively. Fig. 6 illustrates the tight distribution of the control points applied on upper/lower skins, and front/rear spar webs. From Fig. 6, there are 44 control points on upper skin, 42 control points on lower skin, and 7 control points on front and rear spar webs, respectively. The total control points are 100, and the resulting design variables would be $100 \times 3(\text{layers}) = 300$. The loose distribution of control points is illustrated in Fig.7. As shown in Fig.7, there are 27 control points on upper skin, 34 control points on lower skin, and 7 control points on front and rear spar webs, respectively. The total control points are 75, and the resulting design variables would be $75 \times 3(\text{layers}) = 225$.

Figure 6: The control points for the tight distribution

Figure 7: The control points for the loose distribution

5 RESULTS

Fig. 8 shows the converge history of the optimization with the use of bilinear Lagrange shape function approach with two different distribution of control points, 100 and 75, respectively. As shown in Fig. 8(a), with the use of 100 control points, the converged solution is achieved after 90 iterations when 20% flutter margin constraint is considered, and the weight reduction is about 159.7kg (7.01%). When considering 25% flutter margin constraint, the optimization is converged after 166 iterations, and the weight reduction is about 109.3kg (4.8%). Therefore, in order to expand the flutter envelope, more structure weight is needed to compensate the aeroelastic stability requirement. The similar remarks can also be drawn from the analysis of Fig 8(b). Furthermore, from Fig8(a) and Fig8(b), it is also observed if more control points are used for the shape function, more structure weight reduction can be obtained.

Table 2 further illustrates the wing structure weight reduction with different setting of control points and flutter constraints. As shown in Table 2, in order to increase the flutter boundary by 5% margin, at least 50kg additional structure weight is needed.

Figure 8: The convergence history of optimization process with the use of shape function approach.

Structure Type	Baseline wing	20% margin with 100 points	25% margin with 100 points	20% margin with 75 points	25% margin with 75 points
Skin	1212.3 [kg]	1073 [kg]	1098 [kg]	1105 [kg]	1149 [kg]
Spar web	319.8 [kg]	333.2 [kg]	333.7 [kg]	331.2 [kg]	338 [kg]
Stringer/spar cab	744.5 [kg]	710.7 [kg]	735.6 [kg]	709.3 [kg]	719.7 [kg]
Total weight	2276.6 [kg]	2116.9 [kg]	2167.3 [kg]	2145.5 [kg]	2206.7 [kg]
Total reduction	-	159.7 [kg]	109.3 [kg]	131.1 [kg]	69.9 [kg]
Percent of reduction	-	7.01%	4.8%	5.76%	3.07%

Table 2: Comparison of the wing structure weight reduction

Fig.9~Fig. 13 illustrate the skin thickness and the spar web thickness of the baseline and optimized wing structures under four cases using shape function approach, respectively. The thickness used in these figures is the number of plies. It is easily seen that, the thickness distribution has been changed after the aeroelastic tailoring. Since the flutter boundary of the baseline wing does not satisfy the aeroelastic stability requirements, i.e., the baseline wing does not satisfy the aeroelastic stability requirements. Therefore, a further structure optimization and design is required. Through the aeroelastic tailoring, the thickness distribution can be changed to reach both the structure weight saving and flutter stability requirement.

	Bay1	Bay2	Bay3	Bay4	Bay5	Bay6	Bay7	Bay8	Bay9	Bay10	Bay11	Bay12	Bay13	Bay14	Bay15	Bay16	Bay17	Bay18	Bay19	Bay20	Bay21	Bay22
FS-STR1	44	44	44																			
STR1-2	44	44	44	54	48	68	80	68														
STR2-3	54	44	44	48	48	68	68	68	58	50	48	48	44									
STR3-4	54	44	44	48	48	56	64	56	50	50	48	48	44	52	40	40	34	34				
STR4-5	54	48	48	48	48	56	64	56	50	50	48	48	44	44	40	40	34	34	34	34	32	24
STR5-6	60	52	52	52	52	56	64	56	50	50	48	48	44	44	40	40	34	34	34	34	32	24
STR6-7	60	56	56	66	66	64	62	56	56	50	48	44	44	44	40	40	34	34	34			
STR7-8	66	66	66	66	66	64	62	62	62	50	48	44	44									
STR8-9	72	72	72	72	74	66	66	68														
STR9-10	72	72	72																			
STR10-RS	72																					

a) upper skin

	Bay1	Bay2	Bay3	Bay4	Bay5	Bay6	Bay7	Bay8	Bay9	Bay10	Bay11	Bay12	Bay13	Bay14	Bay15	Bay16	Bay17	Bay18	Bay19	Bay20	Bay21	Bay22
FS-STR1	38	38	42																			
STR1-2	38	38	42	44	44	62	78	66														
STR2-3	42	42	42	44	44	62	66	66	46	40	38	40	40									
STR3-4	56	50	56	56	56	62	66	66	50	48	48	48	40	44	40	36	32	32	28	28	22	22
STR4-5	56				70																	
STR5-6	56				70																	
STR6-7	64	64	76	76	70	70	66	58	50	48	48	48	40	44	40	36	32	32	28	28	22	22
STR7-8	64	64	64	70	70	70	66	58	46	42	40	40	40									
STR8-9	64	64	64	64	70	70	66	62														
STR9-10	64	64	64																			
STR10-RS	64																					

b) lower skin

	Bay1	Bay2	Bay3	Bay4	Bay5	Bay6	Bay7	Bay8	Bay9	Bay10	Bay11	Bay12	Bay13	Bay14	Bay15	Bay16	Bay17	Bay18	Bay19	Bay20	Bay21	Bay22
FS-WEB	42	42	42	38	46	62	78	62	54	46	46	46	46	40	32	32	32	32	24	24	24	24
RS-WEB	62	62	68	94	78	74	74	74	64	64	56	48	42	32	32	32	32	32	24	24	24	24

c) front and rear spar

Figure 9: Illustration of the thickness of the baseline wing structure.

	Bay1	Bay2	Bay3	Bay4	Bay5	Bay6	Bay7	Bay8	Bay9	Bay10	Bay11	Bay12	Bay13	Bay14	Bay15	Bay16	Bay17	Bay18	Bay19	Bay20	Bay21	
FS-STR1	37	45	54																			
STR1-2	31	39	47	55	58	52	39	36														
STR2-3	34	37	40	43	46	48	40	39	56	64	64	64	61									
STR3-4	36	37	37	38	41	46	41	42	59	64	59	53	51	51	49	44	38	33				
STR4-5	38	38	39	39	41	45	43	44	53	55	50	45	43	43	41	36	32	31	33	29	25	
STR5-6	40	40	40	40	41	44	48	52	52	50	46	41	40	42	40	35	29	29	34	33	29	
STR6-7	42	42	41	40	41	42	56	66	57	51	46	41	42	48	47	39	30	27	28			
STR7-8	43	45	47	48	47	44	60	74	64	57	49	42	43									
STR8-9	41	50	58	67	65	50	60	75														
STR9-10	45	58	70																			
STR10-RS	55																					

a) upper skin

	Bay1	Bay2	Bay3	Bay4	Bay5	Bay6	Bay7	Bay8	Bay9	Bay10	Bay11	Bay12	Bay13	Bay14	Bay15	Bay16	Bay17	Bay18	Bay19	Bay20	Bay21	Bay22
FS-STR1	34	39	43																			
STR1-2	30	35	39	44	44	39	34	34														
STR2-3	30	33	35	37	38	36	37	42	49	52	50	47	51									
STR3-4	31	31	31	32	33	34	43	50	56	58	56	54	54	60	61	54	47	39	31	27	27	27
STR4-5	31				32																	
STR5-6	33				36																	
STR6-7	34	35	37	38	41	44	46	59	62	90	82	73	63	51	43	37	31	27	23	21	23	24
STR7-8	33	38	42	45	47	47	49	66	88	93	77	61	49									
STR8-9	33	40	47	53	54	49	52	72														
STR9-10	36	45	53																			
STR10-RS	45																					

b) lower skin

	Bay1	Bay2	Bay3	Bay4	Bay5	Bay6	Bay7	Bay8	Bay9	Bay10	Bay11	Bay12	Bay13	Bay14	Bay15	Bay16	Bay17	Bay18	Bay19	Bay20	Bay21	Bay22
FS-WEB	44	42	40	38	36	35	33	32	31	30	35	46	57	63	64	59	47	35	28	25	21	
RS-WEB	56	78	100	126	122	108	96	80	64	47	39	38	37	34	29	24	21	21	21	21	21	21

c) front and rear spar

Figure 10: Illustration of the optimized structure thickness with 20% flutter constraints and 100 control points.

	Bay1	Bay2	Bay3	Bay4	Bay5	Bay6	Bay7	Bay8	Bay9	Bay10	Bay11	Bay12	Bay13	Bay14	Bay15	Bay16	Bay17	Bay18	Bay19	Bay20	Bay21	Bay22
FS-STR1	37	46	55																			
STR1-2	31	39	47	56	57	49	37	34														
STR2-3	34	37	40	43	45	47	38	38	54	64	74	84	78									
STR3-4	37	37	37	38	40	44	39	41	62	71	65	60	55	52	48	43	38	31				
STR4-5	38	39	39	40	41	41	44	39	62	67	57	47	42	40	38	35	31	32	33	28	25	21
STR5-6	40	40	40	41	41	41	41	46	62	61	51	41	37	39	38	33	29	30	36	34	29	27
STR6-7	42	42	41	40	41	42	59	70	61	53	47	40	41	48	48	39	30	25	24			
STR7-8	43	45	47	48	48	44	64	79	65	57	48	40	42									
STR8-9	41	50	58	67	65	49	62	79														
STR9-10	44	58	70																			
STR10-RS	55																					

a) upper skin

	Bay1	Bay2	Bay3	Bay4	Bay5	Bay6	Bay7	Bay8	Bay9	Bay10	Bay11	Bay12	Bay13	Bay14	Bay15	Bay16	Bay17	Bay18	Bay19	Bay20	Bay21	Bay22
FS-STR1	35	39	43																			
STR1-2	30	35	39	44	44	40	34	32														
STR2-3	30	33	36	38	38	37	39	45	50	52	52	52	58									
STR3-4	31	31	32	33	34	34	50	59	61	62	62	62	61	63	63	56	48	39	30	25	25	26
STR4-5	31				32		46															
STR5-6	33				35		43															
STR6-7	33	35	36	36	40	46	40	50	86	100	90	79	67	53	43	37	31	27	23	21	22	23
STR7-8	33	39	43	47	48	44	38	60	100	111	85	57	40									
STR8-9	33	43	52	61	58	41	37	70														
STR9-10	35	48	60																			
STR10-RS	42																					

b) lower skin

	Bay1	Bay2	Bay3	Bay4	Bay5	Bay6	Bay7	Bay8	Bay9	Bay10	Bay11	Bay12	Bay13	Bay14	Bay15	Bay16	Bay17	Bay18	Bay19	Bay20	Bay21	Bay22
FS-WEB	44	42	40	37	36	35	33	32	31	30	36	51	65	71	69	67	60	47	35	28	24	21
RS-WEB	56	78	101	127	122	108	95	78	62	44	35	34	33	30	27	23	21	21	21	21	21	21

c) front and rear spar

Figure 11: Illustration of the optimized structure thickness with 25% flutter constraints and 100 control points.

	Bay1	Bay2	Bay3	Bay4	Bay5	Bay6	Bay7	Bay8	Bay9	Bay10	Bay11	Bay12	Bay13	Bay14	Bay15	Bay16	Bay17	Bay18	Bay19	Bay20	Bay21	Bay22
FS-STR1	37	46	55																			
STR1-2	37	44	51	55	53	52	52	52														
STR2-3	37	42	47	49	48	48	50	51	54	57	61	61	56	50	45	44	40	31				
STR3-4	37	40	43	45	43	44	48	51	54	57	61	58	55	54	57	59	53	47	39	29	25	26
STR4-5	37	38	40	40	38	41	46	51	52	49	46	45	44	43	39	33	32	34	33	27	24	21
STR5-6	38	40	42	42	40	42	47	53	54	47	41	38	40	42	39	31	29	33	37	34	29	27
STR6-7	42	45	49	50	47	49	53	59	58	52	45	43	45	48	46	38	33	29	24			
STR7-8	45	50	56	58	55	55	59	64	64	57	49	47	49									
STR8-9	48	55	63	67	64	62	65	69														
STR9-10	52	61	71																			
STR10-RS	54																					

a) upper skin

	Bay1	Bay2	Bay3	Bay4	Bay5	Bay6	Bay7	Bay8	Bay9	Bay10	Bay11	Bay12	Bay13	Bay14	Bay15	Bay16	Bay17	Bay18	Bay19	Bay20	Bay21	Bay22
FS-STR1	35	38	42																			
STR1-2	29	34	38	42	45	46	45	45														
STR2-3	30	32	34	36	39	43	46	49	50	49	50	52	57									
STR3-4	31	31	31	31	34	40	47	53	59	61	58	55	54	57	59	53	47	39	29	25	25	26
STR4-5	32				32		48															
STR5-6	33				33		52															
STR6-7	34	34	34	34	39	48	57	66	76	80	77	74	66	53	43	37	31	27	23	21	22	23
STR7-8	33	37	41	44	49	56	63	71	78	77	68	57	48									
STR8-9	33	41	48	55	61	65	70	75														
STR9-10	36	46	56																			
STR10-RS	46																					

b) lower skin

	Bay1	Bay2	Bay3	Bay4	Bay5	Bay6	Bay7	Bay8	Bay9	Bay10	Bay11	Bay12	Bay13	Bay14	Bay15	Bay16	Bay17	Bay18	Bay19	Bay20	Bay21	Bay22
FS-WEB	43	41	40	38	36	35	34	32	31	30	35	45	56	62	62	63	57	45	33	26	24	21
RS-WEB	56	78	100	126	122	108	95	79	63	46	38	37	34	34	29	24	21	21	21	21	21	21

c) front and rear spar

Figure 12: Illustration of the optimized structure thickness with 20% flutter constraints and 75 control points.

	Bay1	Bay2	Bay3	Bay4	Bay5	Bay6	Bay7	Bay8	Bay9	Bay10	Bay11	Bay12	Bay13	Bay14	Bay15	Bay16	Bay17	Bay18	Bay19	Bay20	Bay21	Bay22
FS-STR1	37	45	54																			
STR1-2	37	43	51	54	53	50	47	44														
STR2-3	37	42	47	49	48	48	47	47	54	72	92	94	77									
STR3-4	37	40	43	45	44	46	49	52	56	62	71	72	63	53	46	45	41	32				
STR4-5	37	38	40	41	41	44	49	56	57	55	52	50	47	44	39	33	32	34	33	27	24	21
STR5-6	38	40	42	42	42	46	52	59	59	52	44	40	41	42	39	31	29	33	37	34	29	27
STR6-7	42	45	49	50	49	51	56	62	62	54	46	43	45	48	46	38	33	29	24			
STR7-8	45	50	56	58	55	56	61	65	64	56	48	45	48									
STR8-9	49	55	63	67	64	62	65	68														
STR9-10	52	61	71																			
STR10-RS	55																					

a) upper skin

	Bay1	Bay2	Bay3	Bay4	Bay5	Bay6	Bay7	Bay8	Bay9	Bay10	Bay11	Bay12	Bay13	Bay14	Bay15	Bay16	Bay17	Bay18	Bay19	Bay20	Bay21	Bay22
FS-STR1	35	38	42																			
STR1-2	30	34	38	42	44	44	44	41														
STR2-3	30	32	34	36	39	44	47	50	50	49	54	59	66									
STR3-4	31	31	31	30	35	44	53	60	69	71	67	63	61	63	63	57	50	41	30	25	25	26
STR4-5	32				33		54															
STR5-6	33				33		57															
STR6-7	33	34	34	34	39	51	61	73	83	90	87	83	73	55	43	37	31	27	23	21	22	23
STR7-8	33	38	43	46	52	61	69	78	86	83	71	58	46									
STR8-9	33	43	52	62	69	73	77	82														
STR9-10	37	50	62																			
STR10-RS	48																					

b) lower skin

	Bay1	Bay2	Bay3	Bay4	Bay5	Bay6	Bay7	Bay8	Bay9	Bay10	Bay11	Bay12	Bay13	Bay14	Bay15	Bay16	Bay17	Bay18	Bay19	Bay20	Bay21	Bay22
FS-WEB	44	42	40	37	36	34	33	32	31	30	36	50	63	69	68	62	49	37	29	25	21	21
RS-WEB	56	78	101	127	123	109	96	81	65	48	39	38	36	33	28	24	21	21	21	21	21	21

c) front and rear spar

Figure 13: Illustration of the optimized structure thickness with 25% flutter constraints and 75 control points.

The evaluation of the flutter boundaries of the baseline and optimized wing structure with 75 control points are shown in Fig. 14. It is observed that, the flutter boundary of the baseline wing crosses the 15% flutter margin envelope, but the flutter margins of the optimized wing structure with two different flutter margin constraints satisfy the desired 15% of margin of the aeroelastic envelope at all mach number condition.

Figure 14: The flutter boundary comparison of the baseline and the optimized wing structure with 75 control points

The maximum ply drop layers of the baseline and optimized wing at adjacent elements are shown in Table 3. It can be seen that, the maximum ply drop layer is smaller when less control points are applied. It means that the thickness distribution is smoother while 75 control points are used, compared to 100 control points. Furthermore, increase of the flutter margin constraint results in a less smooth distribution of the wing thickness. Compared to the baseline wing, the optimized wing may be less smooth due to a demand for higher flutter margin constraints. However, under an appropriate condition, such as the case of 75 control points and 20% margin envelope, the result of aeroelastic tailoring can be smoother than that of the baseline wing. Therefore, aeroelastic tailoring is really effective to obtain an optimized structure through a trade-off study of the weight saving, flutter stability and composite ply-up manufacturing, and so on.

Maximum ply drop layer	Baseline wing	20% margin with 100 points	25% margin with 100 points	20% margin with 75 points	25% margin with 75 points
Upper skin	20	19	24	17	22
Lower skin	20	23	40	18	27
Front and rear spar	26	26	26	26	26

Table 3: Maximum ply drop layers at adjacent elements of baseline and optimization wing.

9 CONCLUSION

In this paper, an aeroelastic tailoring design study of a composite wing with the use of the bilinear Lagrange shape function approach is investigated. The number of control points used among optimization can influence the thickness distribution of the wing. When 75 control points are used, the thickness is smoother than one of 100 control points. Meanwhile, the increasing of flutter margin can compensate a part of weight saving. The optimized wing structure can be smoother than the baseline wing with a proper setting of the control points and the flutter constraints. Through this study, it is demonstrated that the bilinear Lagrange shape function is an efficient approach to be used in the structure sizing of a composite wing structure.

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